

Peculiarities of legal regulation of superficies as a type of limited property right

Zufarova Kamila Rustamovna

Applicant of the Department of Civil Law
Tashkent State Law University

Annotation: The article characterizes the features of legal regulation of superficies as a type of limited property right, as a legal institution regulating the right to develop a land plot, the legal nature of superficies, the grounds for establishing, terminating superficies and its legal consequences, relevance and significance at the present time, in modern law

Key words: limited property rights, legal regulation of superficies, grounds for establishing and terminating superficies, legal structure of superficies, legal consequences, property rights, development rights.

Limited property rights to land are recognized by virtually all modern legal systems. These rights can be divided into two groups: some are aimed at protecting the interests of individuals (e.g., usufruct), while others facilitate more efficient use of resources (e.g., emphyteusis and superficies).

Superficies, which has its ancient roots in Ancient Rome, was adopted by many legal systems as a result of the reception of Roman law. Currently, the right to build is recognized and regulated in the legislation of countries such as Austria, Belgium, Germany and Italy. This institution is often introduced to solve housing problems, but it is also used for the construction of non-residential buildings.

In German civil law, the question of the nature of the right to an erected building remained the subject of extensive discussion for a long time, and by the 19th century several theories had emerged to explain its legal nature.

The first of these, the theory of divided property, was based on the concept of supreme and subordinate property (dominium directum and dominium utile). This theory, developed by the glossators, was widely spread in Germany and Austria. Within the framework of this theory, supreme property was interpreted as the right to the substance of a thing, while subordinate property was considered as the right of use with some rights of disposal. However, with the transition from the feudal system to the bourgeois system, this theory lost its relevance and significance.

As an alternative, a theory was put forward according to which the right to use a land plot for construction is recognized as a real or personal servitude[1]. Opponents of this theory pointed out some of its shortcomings: firstly, a real servitude requires the

presence of a dominant and service position of the plots, whereas a superficies does not have such a requirement; secondly, the superficies have a targeted nature related to the construction and operation of the building, which does not correspond to the concept of an easement; thirdly, the superficies can be alienated and transferred by inheritance, which is impossible for an easement.

When forming the theory of development law, German civilists took into account both the pandectic doctrine and the property needs of the time. As a result, a decision was made to recognize the building, erected on the basis of the right of development, as an integral part of the inherited right of development and to extend to it the right of the regime of immovable property, which made it possible to encumber it with a mortgage.

According to Article 779 of the Swiss Civil Code of 1907, a plot of land could be encumbered with a right granting a third party the right to erect and operate a building above or below the surface of the plot[2], which was known as a superficies. In accordance with this norm, the right of ownership of the constructed structures is transferred to the person who has been granted the right of development. However, upon expiration of the superficies, the right of ownership of the buildings is returned to the owner of the land plot, and the developer is paid compensation for the constructed objects[3].

This legal structure reflects an attempt to balance the interests of both the land owner and the land user by providing clear rules regarding the ownership of erected buildings and the procedure for compensation for improvements made. However, this mechanism may also create certain complications, such as the need to accurately determine the value of compensation and possible disputes about the condition of buildings when transferring ownership.

In a number of jurisdictions, such as Italy, Spain[4] and Argentina, the law recognizes the developer's right of ownership of the structures erected on the land. This provision reflects the concept that the rights to the land and the structures erected on it can be separated.

In France, historically, the legal system has sought to restore a single right of ownership of real estate. However, practices challenging this unity have been recognized by the Court of Cassation, which has confirmed the possibility of spatial division of the right. This means that a person may have a right to use the space above or below ground, which may in effect amount to a right of ownership. Current French law reinforces this by allowing persons with building rights to be the owners of the buildings for the duration of the right. Thus, there may be several owners within the same space, which creates the possibility of clearly delineating the rights to the land and to the buildings[5].

The issue of the developer's rights regarding buildings erected on a plot of land is often resolved in various legal systems within the framework of temporary property rights[6]. In this case, the developer receives the right to construct and operate the building for a certain period, after which the ownership of the buildings passes to the owner of the land. In some systems, this is accompanied by the payment of compensation to the

developer for the erected structures, in others - without it.

In Ukrainian legislation, superficies was normatively enshrined relatively recently, but today its use is quite widespread. Despite the wide recognition of this institution, the normative regulation of superficies remains limited and contains noticeable gaps. On the one hand, this creates space for different interpretations and approaches, and on the other, it allows for flexible regulation of legal relations between the landowner and the developer.

In the Civil Code of Ukraine, Chapter 34 (Articles 413–417) is devoted to superficies, and in the Land Code, Chapter 161 (Article 102-1) is devoted to them. According to Article 413 of the Civil Code, the owner of a land plot has the right to grant it for use to another person for the construction of various structures and buildings.

Superficies may arise on the basis of a contract or a will, they are a compensated right, which means that the owner of the land has the right to receive payment for the use of the plot. The superficies agreement determines the scope of rights of both the owner of the land plot and the land user (superficiary).

According to Article 295 of the Civil Code of Ukraine, superficies are considered as a type of property rights to someone else's property, which requires mandatory state registration in accordance with Article 4 of the Law of Ukraine "On State Registration of Property Rights to Real Estate and Their Encumbrances".

In civil law, a distinction is made between property rights and obligatory rights, and while property rights concern a specific thing, obligatory rights concern actions or inactions. There is no direct definition of property rights in Ukrainian legislation, but it was enshrined in the previously effective Decree of the President of Ukraine "On state registration of rights to real estate" dated 16.06.1999 No. 666/99, according to which property rights represented the legally established dominance of a person over a thing and had to be protected from violations.

In civil law theory, property rights are subjective rights that allow one to extract useful properties from a certain thing. Property rights are absolute, that is, they are protected from encroachment by an unlimited number of subjects of civil circulation.

A thing is defined as an object of the material world (Article 179 of the Civil Code of Ukraine), and a land plot is qualified as an immovable thing (Article 181 of the Civil Code of Ukraine). According to Article 190 of the Civil Code, things are property, and all property rights are property rights by their nature.

In relation to superficies, this right is considered as a property right to a thing, which implies its consideration as property without a physical body, or, in other words, incorporeal property.

It is important to distinguish between a land plot as real estate and a superficies as a property right, since they differ as different objects of civil rights, with a different legal status and legal regulation, since a land plot can be alienated separately from a superficies. Article 414 of the Civil Code establishes that the transfer of ownership of land provided

for development does not affect the right to the structure built on the site. At the same time, the superficic has the right to alienate his superficic, except in cases concerning state and municipal lands.

Article 415 of the Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan establishes the right of ownership of the land user to buildings and structures constructed on the land plot. In the event of transfer of ownership of the building, the new person receives the right to use the land plot on the same terms as the previous owner.

However, when superficics are terminated, the legislator grants the parties the right to independently determine the consequences of the termination of the right of superficics in the presence of a constructed object (Article 417 of the Civil Code). In the absence of an agreement, the owner of the land has the right to demand the demolition of the building and the restoration of the site to its original state. The law also provides for a scenario where demolition may be prohibited or inappropriate, and the court may decide to buy out the land or building and establish new conditions for the use of the land.

A superficic is an independent negotiable object of civil rights, which can be freely alienated (Part 2 of Article 413 of the Civil Code). In accordance with Part 4 of Article 12 of the Civil Code, property rights can be transferred by contract and a superficic can be sold, donated or exchanged.

When alienating a superficics, the consent of the landowner is not required, although the agreement may establish restrictions. Unlike a lease agreement, the sale of a lease right can be contested, since it involves the disposal of land and the principles of alienation of a superficics are similar to the right of lease, but with key differences.

The confusion of superficics with land lease is due to insufficient regulatory framework for superficics. Thus, the Supreme Court of Ukraine in a letter dated 01.07.2013 noted that legal relations based on superficics and land lease are regulated by different legal norms, and the same rules should not be applied to both legal institutions, since the termination of superficics is regulated by special norms of civil and land legislation.

Article 416 of the Civil Code of Ukraine specifies the following grounds for termination of superficics, such as:

1. The unification of the land owner and land user in one person, which may occur if the land owner acquires a superficics from the superficier.
2. Expiry of the right of use.
3. Refusal of the land user of the right of use.
4. Non-use of the land plot for construction for three consecutive years.

Part six of Article 1021 of the Land Code of Ukraine includes the following grounds in the already mentioned ones:

1. Alienation of a privately owned land plot for public needs or due to public necessity.
2. Adoption by an authorized body of a decision on the use of a state or municipal

land plot for public needs.

3. Termination of an agreement concluded within the framework of a state-legal partnership (under agreements concluded within the framework of such partnership).

Thus, the law directly provides for the conditions under which superficies are terminated. If the destruction of a building constructed on a plot of land is not grounds for termination of superficies, then non-use of the land for three years is considered as such.

Part 2 of Article 416 of the Civil Code of Ukraine deserves special attention, as it legally establishes the termination of the right to use land by a court decision and in other cases established by law. A literal interpretation of this legal norm presupposes clarification of the specified "other cases" that must be expressly provided for by law.

Of particular interest is the judicial practice on this issue, namely the position of the Kyiv City Court of Appeal, set out in the ruling of 01.11.2017 in case No. 760/442/17, where the court decided that "other cases established by law" include general rules on termination of contracts. The court justified this by the fact that upon termination of the contract, any obligations and rights of the parties that arose on the basis of the contract cease, and, consequently, the superficiary has no legal grounds for continuing to use the land plot.

However, when analyzing this position from the point of view of legislation, it is necessary to state that, firstly, the superficies agreement and the concept of superficies themselves are not identical concepts, just as a court decision to terminate a superficies agreement and a decision to terminate superficies are not identical. Part 2 of Article 416 of the Civil Code of Ukraine provides for the termination of superficies, not the termination of the contract, and does not establish a new basis for the termination of superficies, but describes the judicial procedure for the termination of superficies in the presence of grounds established by law (many lawyers mistakenly interpret this rule as adding a new basis for the termination of superficies).

Furthermore, the need to clarify the concept of "grounds established by law" is dictated. It seems that the letter of the Supreme Court of Ukraine dated 01.07.2013, which emphasizes that the norms of the Land and Civil Codes establish the grounds for termination of the right to use a land plot for development, including the redemption of a land plot due to public need (Article 350 of the Civil Code), refers to this basis.

Thus, Part 2 of Article 651 of the Civil Code of Ukraine does not include the existence of a land user's debt to the land owner as grounds for termination of superficies, unlike leases, where non-payment of rent may be grounds for termination of the lease agreement.

A scientific and legal examination conducted by the V.M. Koretsky Institute of State and Law of the National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine indicates that the violation of the payment obligation by the superficie is not grounds for terminating the superficie, although the owner may collect the debt by force.

This approach was also typical for Roman private law. As O.A. Kruglova notes, the

owner could provide superficies free of charge. In the event of the superficies evading payment, the owner could collect the debt, but could not terminate the contract for the provision of superficies[7].

In addition, the court in the given definition speaks of the termination of all obligations and rights arising on the basis of the contract. However, the law indicates that the legal consequence of the termination of the contract is the termination of obligations (Part 2 of Article 653 of the Civil Code of Ukraine), and not rights, since the rights generated by the contract do not always terminate along with the contract.

Thus, the right of ownership of the item manufactured under the contract is retained by the customer even upon termination of the contract. The Resolution of the Supreme Court of Ukraine dated 20.02.2013 No. 6-158cs12 states that the right of ownership that arose before the dispute over termination of the contract does not automatically cease upon its termination. The parties may not demand the return of anything that was performed before the change or termination of the contract, unless otherwise provided by the contract or by law.

Thus, the result of the execution of the superficies contract is the emergence of a property right, which cannot be automatically terminated due to the termination of the contract. If the superficies were transferred to a third party, the rights of this person as a bona fide purchaser are protected by law.

Therefore, superficies are a property right that allows one to own and use a land plot for the construction of buildings and structures, as well as to obtain ownership of the erected buildings. The superficies are established on the basis of a contract or a will, and can be transferred and encumbered with a pledge. The framework of the superficies is determined by the terms of the contract between the superficies and the owner of the land.

A superficic is not just a contract, and not an obligation, although it may arise on the basis of a contract; the superficic itself and the contract establishing it are different concepts. Termination of the contract terminates the obligations, but does not always lead to automatic termination of the property right, and if the superficic was lawfully transferred to a third party, the rights of that party are protected by law.

Superficies, as one of the oldest legal institutions regulating the right to develop a land plot, still retains its relevance today, in modern law. This legal institution, which originated in Ancient Rome, has spread to the legal systems of many countries. Superficies grant a land user the right to erect and operate buildings on someone else's land plot on the basis of a contract or will, while the landowner retains ownership of the plot itself. However, despite its widespread recognition, there are many controversial issues regarding the legal consequences of establishing and terminating this right.

The basis of superficies is a contract that defines the conditions for using a land plot for construction. This contractual obligation determines the scope of rights of both the land owner and the superficic, and also establishes mandatory payments for the use of the land. The problem is that many lawyers in practice mix superficies with leases, which leads to

legal conflicts. While leases imply temporary use of a land plot, superficies can provide broader rights, including ownership of the erected buildings.

The legal nature of superficies, like other property rights, implies their inalienability from a specific object - a land plot or building. This is also confirmed by the fact that the superficium may freely alienate his right to third parties without obtaining the consent of the land owner.

The legislation of many countries establishes clear grounds for termination of superficies, such as the unification of rights to land and a building in one person, expiration of the term of the right, refusal of the land user or non-use of the land.

The issue of judicial termination of superficies on other grounds seems to be of no small importance. Judicial practice gives rise to discussions regarding the termination of the superficies agreement and its legal consequences. One of the problems is the understanding that termination of the contract does not always lead to automatic termination of the property right, since the superficies may be alienated before the termination of the contract, and the rights of a bona fide purchaser are guaranteed by law. This causes certain difficulties, especially in the context of a possible conflict between the landowner and the superficies.

Another controversial issue is the legal fate of buildings erected on a land plot after the termination of the superficies. Some researchers point to the need to demolish buildings in the event of the expiration of the contract or its termination, while others insist on the possibility of their purchase by the owner of the land or the superficies. However, the legislation gives the parties freedom to determine the future fate of the constructed objects, which may lead to legal disputes in the absence of mutual agreement.

In conclusion, superficies as a legal institution have flexibility and potential for effective regulation of land relations. However, insufficient legal regulation and the ambiguity of a number of norms give rise to the need for further clarification and adaptation of legislation. The development of judicial practice also plays an important role in the formation of approaches to resolving conflicts related to the termination of superficies and protecting the rights of the parties involved in these legal relations.

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